

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B121
 Date: 11 Aug 2005
 Take Off: 12:58:46
 Landing: 16:50:31
 Flight Time: 3h50m31

Campaign: ICEPIC
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: N Wales

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsey Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Jonathan Smith	Leeds University
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	CVI/CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
8	Mission Scientist Training	Steve Abel	FAAM
9	CPI	Keith Bower	Manchester University
10	AMS	Gerard Capes	Manchester University
11	Core Chem / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
12			
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b121
 Date: 11/8/05
 Project: ICEPIC
 Location: Wales

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
124912		inu to nav	0.00 kft	003	
125339		taxy start	0.00 kft	017	52'12.55N, 0'10.45E
125846		T/O	-.02 kft	231	from cambridge
133754		jw/nevz	18.1 kft	323	zero
134012	140503	Profile 1	19.9 - 0.44 kft	324	
135607		Profile 1	4.5 kft	288	500 ft/min
140022		Profile 1	2.0 kft	286	interrupt
140139		Profile 1	2.0 kft	027	resume
140558	142501	Run 1	0.46 - 0.44 kft	097	
141550		Run 1	0.46 kft	269	aircraft turn 141208 to 141422
144828	150140	Run 2	11.5 kft	147	
150315		jw nevz zero	11.5 kft	350	
150331	150403	Run 3	11.5 kft	351	
150722	151151	Run 4	14.0 kft	009	
151029		jw nevz zero	14.0 kft	008	
151548	152243	Run 5	15.0 kft	193	
151702		jw nevz zero	15.0 kft	187	
152617	153227	Run 6	15.5 kft	023	
153629	153853	Run 7	16.0 kft	184	
153829		jw/nevz zero	16.0 kft	192	
155206	155243	Run 8	10.0 kft	003	
155444	155525	Run 9	9.9 kft	104	
155825	155944	Run 10	10.5 - 10.4 kft	007	
155853		jw/nevz zero	10.5 kft	009	
160256	160343	Run 11	10.6 - 10.5 kft	173	
160736	160818	Run 12	10.6 - 10.4 kft	004	
161047	161240	Run 13	9.9 - 9.8 kft	228	
165031		Land	0.05 kft	230	at cambridge
165449		standstill	0.06 kft	199	52'12.56N, 0'10.45E

B121 Track 11-AUG-05

PROJECT BRIEF: ICEPIC – development of ice and precipitation in cumulus clouds.

Scientific Aims: The goal of ICEPIC is to understand and quantify the formation and growth of ice particles in cumulus clouds. We wish to examine:

- ❖ the formation of the first ice due to primary nucleation on ice nuclei (IN)
- ❖ the development of ice via secondary processes such as the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of ice particles
- ❖ other secondary ice production processes, such as evaporative break-up;
- ❖ the production of supercooled raindrops and their role in the glaciation process
- ❖ the dependence of these processes on the dynamics of the cloud
- ❖ the production of precipitation

As a first priority, in-situ aerosol and microphysical measurements from the aircraft will be gathered in close coordination with the CAMRa radar at Chilbolton, Hants. Measurements will be made in cumulus clouds when their tops are about 0°C through to when the tops have grown to about -20°C. The radar may identify columns of supercooled raindrops within the growing cumulus clouds that can be investigated more intensively by the aircraft.

Weather conditions: Developing showers that are forecast to have tops up to about -15°C within range of the Chilbolton radar. A section of air free of ice crystals from higher or older clouds. It may be preferable to fly to an alternative region away from the radar if conditions are more suitable.

Safety: Regions that paint RED on the aircraft weather radar should be avoided. No flight into clouds known to be producing lightning. Information on current location of lightning (sferics) can be provided by FAAM using the NAMIS system. Several aircraft may be operating in the CSIP region boundary layer at the same time: UFAM Cessna - entire project; NERC DO-228 - August. (The BAS Twin Otter may also participate in CSIP. The German DO-128 left on 17 July)

Key instruments and their operation

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- GPS (including GPS Cruciform at 20 Hz), INU, turbulence probe
When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager & PIs to monitor turbulence probe signals (TBPC & TBPD) for signs of icing (loss of variability, drop in signal). ICEX to be used on radome, water traps empty.
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC.
When straight & level in clear air, zero / calibrate and note in the Flight Manager's log.
- TWC profile ascents or descents should avoid cloud if possible

Cloud Microphysics & Aerosol

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP (or CIP-100) & PCASP.
Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, pristine ice crystal habits, large drops ($d > 100 \mu\text{m}$) in 2D imagery above freezing level.
- ADA & CPI as above
- SID 2 operated in bursts of 5 minutes to coincide with passing through cloud (to prevent computer crashing)
- CCN measurements should be made by filling the alleviator (2min reqd.) whilst in clear air either below, between or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest. Requires altitude to be held for the 10 min of sample & process.
- AMS minimum 2 min (~12km) reqd for size-resolved composition distribution (out of cloud or Option **B** runs) inlet change & on/off messages copied to Flight Managers log
- CVI below cloud base, normal operation is in aerosol mode. For cloud Option **B** and above cloud base, normal operation is in CVI mode to sample cloud particle residues into the AMS

Key instruments currently unavailable

- *Ice Nucleus counter*
(INC) will normally be operated in clear air and under fixed conditions of temperature and supersaturation so as to maintain it in a stable condition. Allow additional time between runs for the operator to adjust it to different conditions.
- FWVS {to preserve lamp life, switch off when dew point above -15°C}
- SID as for 2D probes

Quicklook to include: TATD & N, DP, LAT, LON, LWC, NEVLW & TW, U, V, W, PHGT, HDG, TAS, TBPC & PD

SORTIE BRIEF: ICEPIC ICE and Precipitation Initiation in Cumulus clouds

Flight Number: B121

Date: 11th August 2005

Mission Scientist: Jonathan Smith

Sortie Aims: To measure development of microphysics and dynamics in cumulus cloud systems.

Location: Amongst developing cumulus clouds within 1-5 hours transit of Cranfield. Showers expected over Wales starting at 10 to 12 UTC, Area Bravo inland and Area Alpha (*most likely to be away from Chilbolton*)

Sortie Summary:

1. Characterise inflow atmosphere around and below developing cumulus – *where not done by CSIP*
2. Penetrate cumulus clouds, preferably near the top of growing turrets, through the updraught. All cloud penetrations should be *with wings level*. Three principal options are for:
 - A well-defined isolated clouds
 - B many clouds (RICO scenario)
 - C organised convection on a convergence line or a gust front.

Meteorological information may be given from the CSIP Operations Centre at Chilbolton before flight and in-flight (using VHF radio, new frequency is 130.575 MHz, call-sign remains “Radsearch”).

Sortie Detail

1. Out-of-Cloud: only where not done by CSIP

- 1.1. Take off and climb for transit to the operating area. Locate suitable growing cumulus. 40+ min
- 1.2. Profile descent in clear air, 1000 ft/min, FL200 to 500 ft agl. If necessary step profile to stay in area. (*Profile optional, not required at Chilbolton*) Set altitudes and directions for later[†]. 25 min
- 1.3. Run at 500 ft agl, minimum time 10 min along suitable azimuth (across line or front for Option C) to sample inflow aerosols & IN. May require initial delay to settle instruments. 10 min
- 1.4. Ascend to 500 ft below cloud base and carry out 10 min run on suitable azimuth to sample inflow aerosols & IN. May require delay after ascent to settle instruments. 15 min

2. Cloud Work Options

Option A: Isolated developing clouds – ascend with clouds, near their top

- A.1. Proceed to about 0° C altitude[†], or below max cloud top if lower 5 min
- A.2. Adjust altitude to 500 ft below cloud top and penetrate cloud. The penetration should be made at a constant azimuth and altitude. It is important to penetrate the growing turret, updraught, region. Once clear of cloud, continue run for 10 s then procedure turn to come back to same region of cloud as quickly as possible. 5 min
- A.3. Repeat A.2 while appropriate, ascending with the top until growth stops or T = -20°C[†]
{ *Vertical separation of repeats set to match growth of cloud*} 45 min
- A.4. Repeat runs at -3 to -8°C T levels where practical, otherwise colder, to measure changes. 15 min

Option B: Many developing cumulus clouds – sample many clouds

- B.1. Proceed to 0° C altitude[†], or max cloud top if lower 5 min
- B.2. Commence 10 min run in along shear direction[†]. Adjust track to randomly sample growing turret / updraught regions of cloud but without passing through RED radar echoes (reflectivities of 37 dBZ or greater). End run clear of cloud. 10 min
- B.3. As time permits, repeat an ascent by -3° C[†] (*approximately 1500 ft*) followed by a run as in B.2 until the lowest of -15° C[†] or max cloud top is reached. (-3, -6, -9, -12, -15° C[†]) 75 min

Option C: Clouds with linear organization (eg. along a convergence line or gust front).

- C.1. Proceed to 0° C[†], or max cloud top if lower 5 min
- C.2. Fly leg perpendicular to line, length as required. Adjust track to penetrate cloud tops or cell centres. End run clear of cloud. 2 min
- C.3. As time permits, repeat a 180° turn and ascent followed by C.2. Ascent either; as A to 500 ft below cloud tops until -20° C[†] reached, or as B at fixed temperature levels. 30+ min

3. Repeat If time permits, for new developing cumulus carry out Option A, B or C.

Transit return at any suitable altitude. 40+ min

2 hours
in area

Missie

Mission Sci: Jonathan Smith

Flight No **B.121**

Date 11th August '05

Page 1 of 6

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Uddo	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Eventually! Delayed t/o, because of weather then further complication of no radar here so have to take aircraft to E. Midlands Airport anyway to get a slight tomorrow (cannot plan a slight with no radar, though if it fails after plan made we can then take alternative action). - need to burn 2 1/2 hrs fuel to land but cannot do a test
					Decide to go for ICEPIC as FAAM cannot authorise that
					Forecast in text from Meto has heavy showers over mountains so will go - despite OBT meso rainy no showers in area NTC must have something to
1258	t/o				From Cambridge hazy 3/8 Ci (Cc) over 3/8 Cu nice looking Cu
1301		4800			Base
1302		6900	← increase on t/o program		some tops + As layer (some above)
1303		9700			As layer - thin
1327				52°N 22°W	different cloud ahead, less Cu below was 5/8, now 3/8 7/8 Ci ahead - old cloud, cirrus? at this level 2/8 As
133953					CPI notes that look like water droplets between layers of cloud As below, 8/8

Mis

Flight No **R 121**
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date **11th August '05**

page **2 of 6**

GMT	F P-	
		d edge of 3/8 AS above - tops look wispy => ice below is water in CPI form above - looks clear
		looks clearer ahead of to N - where we may go.
		52° 8' N 37° W below layer - its more broken here but more extensive than would hope for 3/8 Cu, some building
		B E of us - heading B Snordon
		nice line of cloud seemg to be triggered B the E of us now 52° 9' N 39° W
		Cu building ahead but base is above us T-2-3
13:49		11,200ft
		coming B sea - Cu building over Anglesey
		Menai Straights. Layer of cloud
13 53hh		6000ft Hazy layer re descended, T+7
13 55		picture towards Ireland of cloud in Irish Sea + banking cloud ahead - pass thru tops of banking layer cloud. v. hazy
13 56		0 deg at 680hPa ~ 10,000ft
		hazy layer at 3000 ft.
		PCHest next from 40 counts to 400 in haze
1100	PlinterupA	2000ft broken Sc above us
1104		less haze low down, sea state

Mis

Flight No **R 121**
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Date 11th August '05

Page 3-6

GMT	F P	SPRS (Time, wind, sea state etc.)
1405	R1	ferry to N, passed fishing boat to S
1410		higher ascending Cu to N, becoming hazier
1412		have to turn into haze layer & cannot see the sea - go back to clearer air.
1416		CCN had drilled out - will retake sample PCASP + CO drop drop in CO linked with boat we saw earlier?
1418		v. small boat to South cargo ferry to South
1420		picture of ferry to N
1422		East ferry pictures pass hazy seas were blip in CO complicated hazy picture here growing Cu to N are in vicinity, " " " ahead " " " " higher Cu to S are in danger area!
1428		danger area cloud pictures - can't get them
1429 some		will do CCN run on those higher Cu cloud goes past

1/4 to 1/2 of
 leave at
 1700 local

162

Mis

Flight No **R 121**
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Date 11th August '05

page 4 of 6

GMT	F P	Remarks (visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1450		11,500 ft T-23 just on base of some clouds cu growing up at the land - may play with these
1456 or so		picture of cloud to left in the array! + clouds to get I think that might be worth looking at.
	R2 ed	me to go around as array ahead - nice cloud but its going into danger area! (at beside array)
		out of run T = -6.7
		bit of a messy thing this cloud
1513		2D sees snow CPI sees plates
151610		press noisy cloud now 2 pictures of cloud to side CPI sees drops + ADA sees cloud
151750		break in clouds 2-3 min on 2D
151834		break in cloud T = -9- near base of some cloud its another one again
1505		is turb. ok?
1520		break + the tunnel ahead CPI still sees drops

Flight No **R 121**
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Date 11th August '05

page 5-6

GMT	F P	Remarks (vis, visibility, winds, sea state etc)
	R5	ed of run approach more Cu ahead int reds at +500 ft CPI still sees drops
1525		over lake Vyrnwy above Cc 1/8 As we are operating in 6/8
	R6	run along tops FL155 T-10°C break in the cloud little bit lumpy
1528		line of cu ahead across a break CPI sees agy mixture of ice + water
1533h		run through cloud tops picture zero 8/W + then at end now look through cloud close to lake Bala and Swandam no vchgs
	R8	out of cloud 12 seconds across CPI water + 2D
		view ahead shows that one of the upper cu did graze id precip. onto lower layers
		same height as before 13 s across 2D + (P) water

1815 local
debrief

Miss

Flight No
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B 121

Date 11th August '03

page 6 of 6

GMT	Pr	Remarks
1557		- cloud drifting into airway -
1600		just skim top - larger tops to right wave in airway or beside
	R11	- drops 20+ CPI - downcast at ed, water on midshield
		for R12 will add 500 - too much
	R13	try another cloud and it drops down too low
1617		run through precip. of one of the higher Cu as a test for Ada
1625	52.3 ^N 2.4 ^W	pass nice cloud to North,
162900		pass the top of small cu - bumpy into no echo on radar
1630		pictures taken earlier of Cu to W heading towards Birmingham, large red echo on radar
1638		into cloud, bumpy - nothing on radar
1640		into cloud soon 1740 ³⁴ in 4 hours 2050 and 2100

So - good cloud in the airways,
higher cloud measured but not developing
quickly - not really ice as base at $T = -7^{\circ}\text{C}$
measured cloud at end, but wasn't growing
too much - a basis for the CCN measurements

Instruments CCN, ^{died out} won't pick up max. ||
A'da - died at end

"like a wayward school trip"

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B121

Date: 11/8/05

Operator:papj

Page1 of

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
134012	10	0.09	21								Start pl @ 200
134103	30	0.18	26	1000							190
134202	27	0.7	62	4000	10	800	2	250	2000	2	180
144415	20	0.3	67	10	5	800	2	50	3000	2	160
134508	15	0.09	67								150
134610	60	0.1	67								140
134702	30	0.09	67								130
134809	20	0.08	67								120
134915	20	0.09	67								110
135010	20	0.07	67								100
135110	30	0.08	67								090
135210	30	0.08	67								080
											070
135524	50	0.07	67								050
135641	400	0.09	67								040
135813	450	0.09	67								030
140010	450	0.09	67								020
140325	500	0.1									010
140503											500ft end pl
140558	200	0.09	67	5							Start run 1
1407	300	0.09	67	5							
1409	450	0.09	67	10							
1411	900	0.09	67	60							
1415	800	0.09	68	20							
1417	300	0.09	68	5							
1419	250	0.09	68	5							
1421	150	0.08	68	2							
1423	230	0.09	68	5							
142501											End run 1

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B121

Date:11/08/05

Operator:papj

Page 2 of

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
144828											Start run 2
1450	15	0.08	68								
1452	12	0.1	68								
1454	15	0.1	68								
1456	15	0.09	68								
1458	15	0.1	68								
1500	12	0.09	68								
150140											End run 2
											Start run 4
1509	30	0.09	68								
1511	100	0.6	110	5000	2	600	8				
151548											Start run 5
1517	20	0.1	119		1	800	2	100	3000	2	
1519	20	0.5	143	1000	2	800	9	30	2000	9	
1521	10	0.1	177								
152243											End run 5
152625											Start run 6
1527	15	0.3	207	4000	2	800	9				
1529	15	0.09	228	1000	1	300	8				
1531	20	0.3	232	1000	5	800	2	300	3000	2	
153227											End run 6
155444											Start run 9
1555			420								
1559	18	0.09	420								Start 10
1600			430								
160256											Start 11
1604			547								
160736			547								Start 12
161047											Start 13
uii											

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B121**Date:** 11/08/2005

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC B121_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B121_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	08/11/05	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: B121 b) Path name: MFDDATA:B121_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	0 240000	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: B121 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	09/11/05	Note the calibration file used FFSSP_CAL23082005.TXT Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour complete
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B121_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:B121_mfdX','pmsdata:B121_m5procffssp',addt=32 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	09/11/05	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto FFSSP lag 32 sec Corrected manually
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B121_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:B121_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	09/11/05	Complete. FFSSP LWC currently appears v.low wrt JW and Nevzorov

b) Flight number: B121 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10 iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	5	PMSDATA: FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B121_2Dx_IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	11/11/05	Files in: O:\CloudPhysics Core data
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO a) Flight number: B121 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data	0	No correction noted in operator log
e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B121_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: 0 if unkdown i) End time: 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B121_PROC2D	0 130000 165000 0.2 8 / 8 2 11/11/05	Note the particle type complete
10) In PVWAVE i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B121_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B121_M5PROC2D' iii) exit	11/11/05	complete
11) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B121_m5proc2D b) Dataset: mfddata:B121_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	11/11/05	2D concentrations low Some averaging periods too long to include in MFD complete

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT	OFF	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
				1	2	3	4	5	
2:06:10				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
									S D B R P
2:08:30	2:08:55	100ft	28.97 27.6	0.46 0.67 63 144	0.67 125	PAROCS DRT			
				22790 1012.2	2306 1012.3				
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
2:16:30	2:16:54	500ft	28.97 27.6	0.46 275	0.68 1646	1.04 1747	1.33 2000	1.94 3000	S D B R P
				27.5 25.4	1126 2257	285 2259	345 2282	462 2346	Change attitude heading
				24.6 2	1012.2 2	1012.3 3	1012 4	1012.5 5	
2:16:30									
									S D B R P
2:48:40	2:49:13	11.5kft	28.97 27.6	0.5 3925	0.7 478	Quoted peaks not found			
				2622 2273	269 2285				
				968.5	968.7				
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
2:48:46	2:49:13	11.5kft	25.05 23.62	0.49 203	0.71 521	1.07 723	1.39 1221	2.02 1560	S D B R P
				24.01 23.9	309 2308	279 2320	279 2323	285 2329	last voltage estimated from diff in histogram in total V in Sub 1
				24.29 968.7	968.7	968.9	968.9	968.7	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
									S D B R P
									S D B R P

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B121**

Date: 11/08/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	Y	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	Y	Y
Heimann	N		HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	Y	N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	N	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	Y
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SO2	Y	Y	Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	N
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	N
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	N
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	N
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B121

Date: 11/08/05

Instruments

1. Nevzorov vane noted to be u/s pre-flight. Was replaced.
2. DFC intermittently reporting "Motion Alarm Area 1" on screen.

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom H Calls -

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B121:

Log	Reason
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Jonathan Smith
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
ADA/CPI	No log taken or no copy left with FAAM

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

? x ?Forward Facing Cameras
? x ?Rearward Facing Cameras

8mm video recordings from this flight reside with :

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